

Orientalism: The Problematic Of The Term And Present Manifestations, An Applied Study In The Research Of The Orientalist Dimitri Frolov (The Stone In The Holy Qur'an)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Prophet Muhammad , Orientalism, Transformations, Transitions Affected</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5140259</p>	<p><i>The shift from the hostile colonial approach, which we find in the book by many fanatical orientalists, to Orientalism is critical issues in which the pains that are historically related to peace differ from luminous to fascinate the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be upon him and his family) b as an expression of orientalists and success in the righteousness of his people and building the Islamic state These transformations and transitions affected the one who was armed with another in Orientalism, and he is called Ily Nag Rah, by claiming to change. In the approach, especially after the openness between cultures and intellectual exchanges with Islamic countries only, which prevents this term from perpetuating it and remains on it for the R associated with its negative image coupled with an anti-peace view. Only these reasons and their constraints are called by changing the term orientalism i.e. me and other names called by some contemporary orientalists, But the question is, changing the term means a difference for the highest goals and motives, and am I counting, for the indication we do not call it the new Orientalism and the opposite of the previous approach? A and E, respectively, new approaches in their study of non-Islam with the public image and the Qur'an in particular? This is what we will hide through our follow-up to the writings of the orientalists of the Qur'an presented at the thirty-fifth conference on Asian and North African Studies in Budapest in July 1997, which called for the need to change the term x. Roll of a negative character through the position of the Orientalists who are hostile to non-peace and review what the Russian Orientalist Dmitry Frolov presented as a model for that.</i></p>

Introduction

The study included a number of demands, namely

The pain of the first request: The concept of Orientalism, which is the words of researchers in defining Orientalism, these two words are indexed and divided to facilitate determining the meaning of the term. The second requirement: the call to change the term and its causes, and we touched upon the most important reasons for calling Orientalists to change the term and its motives. The third requirement was entitled: Situation Studies in the Contemporary Orientalism of the Qur'an, Dimitri Frolov as a model for the study, with the aim of identifying this call. Has it succeeded in applying new principles as well as the methods used in contemporary Qur'anic studies, including Dimitri's study in line with the scale of contemporary orientalists who advocated changing the term, as was among the studies presented at the conference, the purpose of which was to change the term.

The first requirement: the concept of Orientalism

To clarify the concept of Orientalism, we will review its definition in the language and in the terminology of researchers and specialists in Orientalist studies

First: Defining orientalism in linguistic dictionaries

In order to know what the term should refer to in the dictionaries of the Ely language, Orientalism is derived from the verb (east). It is said: ((The sun rises, it rises in the East and the East: Talaat. The name comes from the bright place [1] and the East shows the meanings of life and existence and this is what went Leh's perspective in explaining the Qur'anic choice of the term "the two easts" in the verse: ((And if he comes and says to me: I hope that you and I will marry after the two easts. Hud / 38); he says: He wanted after the East and the Arab Maghreb, so when he made two, he took control of the word. The sunrise is because the presence of the d and the signifier of Morocco is on non-existence, and the presence. It is certainly more honorable)) ([2]), and from the books of grammar and language in which the Sin refers to the request, which implies that what is meant by Orientalism is to search for the direction of the sunrise. Existence and life, and Orientalism in the figurative expression means a request for guidance for existence and life, and there is no life without sciences. From here,

Orientalism means a search for the center of the radiance of science and knowledge, and what indicates that the meaning of Orientalism in European languages is not a request for the geographical East, but rather a request for the East Related to it, about the moral meaning of brightness, light and guidance, unlike the West, which means decadence and the end, and this is M A paid MazenMatbaghani Muhammad al-Shahed, who has returned to European linguistic dictionaries (German, French and English), is looking for it. A word in the East It was found that the eastern region that is meant by Oriental studies is referred to by the word “characterized by a moral character. It is Morgenland, which means the country of the morning, and it is known that the morning when the sun rises, and this word indicates a shift from geographical and astronomical importance to focusing on the meaning of morning, which includes The meaning of light and wakefulness, and on the other hand we use the word in the Apendland language and means evening country to denote darkness. And rest. (3)

This is what Rudi Barth reveals by saying: ((The middle name is a change in the meaning of the Orient that compares to us Germans - the Slavic world behind the Iron Curtain as it was called in the past - the oases of the region are specialized. By researchers from Eastern and Eastern Europe specializing in Orientalism and geographically located in the southern side Oriental compared to us, and this term dates back to the Middle Ages, but rather to antiquity in which the Mediterranean was as it was said. In the center of the world, and the regions of origin were identified for it, though the word “East” was also exposed for another change in the Its meaning came in the wake of the Arab and Islamic conquests., or if we want to be more precise, it was exposed to the breadth of its connotations, the invaders at that time set out from the Arabian Peninsula, not only to the north and east, but to the west, and they crawled within tens of years, e - The population moved to Sarwen, North Africa, and the population gradually became Arabised, i.e. the Copts in Egypt and the Berbers in the West, and since then Egypt and North African countries are considered among the countries of the East, and Orientalism extends to the smell of West Africa, which is called Morocco, which is the country of sunset. to other countries)) (4) East: to go towards the east ((and east: go east or come east)) (5)

From here we derive

What is meant by the East is not the geographical East, but rather the East associated with science and knowledge, and exclusively the areas reached by the Islamic expansion after the Arab and Islamic conquests.

Second: Defining orientalism in terminology

Presentation in Orientalism in imitation of many possible definitions of researchers and summarized E. Lee chief of the three groups as follows:

1. Group (A): The owners of group (A) see more than Orientalism as a general indicator where they make a note of Orientalism as it is concerned with the heritage of the East in general, including:
2. Abdul-Jabbar Naji FH presented that: ((The science of the languages of the peoples of the East, their heritage, culture, societies, past and present)) (6)
3. Abd al-MutalQasry F.F. presented that his study of the sciences of the Orient and the conditions of its history and beliefs are from the natural environments and the material and human study of such languages and their arguments and the personal natures of the nation in every eastern society, including the study of people and bodies with intellectual and religious currents in their forms, fields and types. (7)
4. Muhammad Baqir al-Hakim, an intervention by F.H (e) (of a cultural and scientific nature to the movement led by a group of Westerners who have branches in their studies of the cultural, social and political conditions of the East, which had an impact) of paramount importance in the cultural life of the East and thus in the intellectual life and social and political)) (8)
5. The orientalist Arbera defined that H: from sailing in the eastern languages, literature and heritage, and therefore Orientalism is the crystallization of eastern languages, literature and heritage (9)

The second group

The proponents of this trend hold that Orientalism is of special importance and that its specialized study is an exclusive part of the middle sciences, which is philology, and from E. Lee in this sense: the Orientalist Rudy Bart, who knew him as - to Iraq - a specialized science of philology (10)

The third group the group

Who gave it general and specific connotations: It is represented in Muhammad Amin's definition in his book Orientalists and the Holy Qur'an that this word - Orientalism - has connotations.

Second: the science of the Middle East or the world in general, and building on this foundation that bears everything related to the knowledge of the East in language and literature, and the effects of art, philosophy and other sciences (11).

Fourth group

They see from the orientalist Badr Aceh the Arab and Islamic world in which R. Malik bin Nabi The Orientalists are: ((The Western Augustus comic book who writes about Islamic thought and Islamic civilization)) (12)

Hence the Orientalists: they are a group of Western researchers who were interested in studying the East in its various religious, linguistic, political and social aspects.

But there are some dilemmas that we face when taking or weighting between these definitions as they do not threaten to be from the East. Is the geographical Middle East or is it ethical (science and science)

The majority of researchers have confined the concept of Orientalism to the Western researcher, which means studying the East, but they will share blood with the launch or release of the passport to a group of researchers who study the East, especially the middle mother Mosul. Christians or Jews with access in Arabic?

To remove this problem, we say that Orientalism has two meanings:

The first: a general meaning, which is the study of the East in general

Second: A study of the Arab and Islamic East in particular, the Orientalist can be defined in this light: Every stranger to Islam, he studied the Islamic East and thus Christians and Jews enter researchers who intend to study the Islamic East. Their origins are not Arab and Western, like Georges Kanawati and other Lebanese orientalist. (13)

The second requirement

The call to change the term and its reasons

Before proceeding to a statement that such an Orientalist term for the position of the West is peace only, as well as creating a term that reflects the image of hostility to Islam, we must look to the only target and ideologues. C. Orientalists called for the study of peace in general and the Qur'an in particular as follows:

First: the goals of orientalism

There were many goals that Orientalism sought to achieve, and they overlapped with each other, and we will limit ourselves to the main goals, which are as follows:

1- Religious goal

E - The launch of Orientalism since its inception is divided into two parts: political and missionary. To achieve this, Christian scientific campaigns were launched to Andalusia and included the Popes of the Church who preceded them in Andalusia in Peter the Great Apostle (1156 AD) to form a group of translators who seek to translate the Holy Qur'an into Latin and learn Islam so that they can achieve their illegitimate goals and present a distorted image of Islam that enables Christianity to keep its themes preventing them from entering Islam, especially after the arrival of the Islamic tide to Constantinople, the capital of the Byzantine Empire, and the emergence of the European Renaissance, which was also the factors of attempts to destroy the church and religious thought (14). This movement reached its climax at the hands of Thomas Aquinas (1232 AD), Roger Bacon (1294 AD) and Raymondale (1316 AD), where Raymondel proposed in 1312 AD the establishment of university educational institutions to undertake the study of Eastern languages. And religions, including Islam and Arabic, as well as for the clergy to study the philosophical views of IbnRushd that contradict IbnRushd's views. the church to respond to and veto; Therefore the resolutions are called Rimondall E. Lee E. The resolution to evangelize and refute E. Peace. (15) Evangelization (16) through Orientalism took ways to evangelize Muslims, and did everything in their power to make Muslims leave their religion, raise doubts, and create a spirit of division among them. Forgetting was not the only goal of orientalism, but the Jews were behind the orientalist movement and preaching. Samuel Zwemer, who headed the evangelization conferences for the sixty years ending in Bhlek in 1952, revealed occult Judaism deep-seated when he asked a rabbi who was studying in the last hours during the torment, we learned that the orientalist Those who studied the East were mainly church fathers and students, so this religious goal included several sub-goals:

1. Fighting Islam and pursuing the shortcomings and highlighting them, claiming that they stem from Judaism and Christianity.
2. Protecting Christians from entering Islam by blurring its features and concealing its facts.
3. Evangelization campaigns and efforts to evangelize Muslims (17).

2- Scientific objective

The scientific goal was the noblest goals of Orientalism. Orientalist Wen Badr Lhasa was one of the achievements of Islamic civilization for the delegation that ended with the advancement of culture and thought for the Lord, and studied these languages, morals and civilization, and helped them translate Arabic and Islamic. Heritage and it can be said that the scientific motivation is represented in three directions (18):

1. Searching for strengths in the Islamic religion and Muslims to benefit from them in the European Renaissance, especially when the Muslims conquered Andalusia. Orientalists were keen to benefit from the sciences of the Islamic East and transfer them to their homelands.
2. The search for knowledge and familiarity with the civilizations, religions and cultures of nations, which are few because they did not study Islam for questioning and so on. Rather, they studied it to find out the reasons for the spread of the Islamic religion.
3. Searching for knowledge of the Islamic religion and working to convey it in a distorted way to European audiences to broadcast the Christian world that the Islamic religion is a religion that does not deserve to be spread, and this is on the one hand, and on the other hand, they seek to spread the ideals of Islam in the hearts of Muslims and prove the superiority of Western civilization.

Some admitted that the Orientalists Z for a scientific goal was not a political goal with them, but rather was a means to missionary goals, as F. Johann says in his book "The History of Orientalism and Orientalists at the

Beginning of Usury in the Nineteenth Century”: ((Orientalism was not purely literary, but It was intended as a response to Islam and a call to Christianity among Muslims, and Arab Islamic biographies (19).

Despite this, some researchers (20) provided examples of the scientific objective, including:

- The French mission headed by Princess Elizabeth, cousin of King Louis of Andalusia, King of France
- The English mission headed by Princess Dobbin, daughter of Prince George of Wales
- Spanish mission

3- Economic goal

Western countries have developed their economy from starch factories, which requires the provision of raw materials on the one hand, and on the other hand, markets need to promote their products. The Arab country was the right center to improve its economy because it had a wealth of natural raw materials, and could also be markets for the disposal of its products. Orientalism and n were the way in ((implementing their projects and economic work as brokers, consultants, translators and prospectors)) (21) and studying the economy of Arab countries and exploring their needs by studying the Arab environment and all its aspects. As for the work that orientalists do in this field, it is to get acquainted with the language of the Arabs, decency and customs, so they were able to conclude treaties in their own language. In 1265 the treaty signed between Tunisia and Pisa was written in Arabic, and France was affected after Italy's trade with the East and contacted the Lebanese trading port of Marseille. Germany established the School of Oriental Languages in 1887 AD to teach these languages to merchants and ambassadors, and an Indian company eliminated Jalan (1715 AD) on his journey to the East to adopt its economic policy on the information he provided to it. . (22)

4- Colonial political goal

Managed colonialism deserved and everyone reaped a wide range of orientalists to serve its purpose and determine the goals of FH in the colony of the country ((as most Western countries wanted political ties between the countries of the Middle East. For eastern countries and the first chairs of oriental languages in major universities and private schools.... and granting them honorary titles and membership from scientific academics)) (23), some orientalists worked as advisors to the foreign ministries of their countries, where politicians would return to orientalists before making their decisions in the affairs of their country. The Arab Politician (24). Just as the politicians participating in conferences at which Bashir preached joined the colonial political conferences of Wen Ili, an example of this is the evangelist Axenfeld, the author of the Islamic side of the report at the conference and president of the Missionary Society in Berlin, said that the most important goals of the conference were discussed only in economics and commerce For Moore as well as the e-decision to include political, economic, and work ethic purposes in the policy of the colonization of Mani, and the aim of the SAS is the introduction of Christianity, the colony of E. Lee Bell Ed also added that Axenfeld should educate patriotic Muslims in Manet schools and sciences rather than Christian schools for their reluctance from their schools Secularism is about the growth and improvement of peace but this is less dangerous than if they are left in the E. SaléMieh schools, some Western governments have funded a number of Orientalist centers. (25)

Second, the reasons for changing the term

It is a youth call Orientalists E .Lee to change the term Orientalism and replace it with other terms are many reasons as possible divided into a youth phenomenon hidden reasons prompted each e Li cascade letters demanding change .And her beauty:

1- The only reasons the phenomenon

It was represented in the reasons mentioned by the orientalists and mentioned in the conferences and symposia that were held. We find controversy over the term among some Western researchers. When Orientalists left him with motives and intentions as a result of unfair effects, some of them decided to use the term Arabism instead of the term Orientalist. Mottabjani stated that Orbancomplained about the term being launched because of the many negative connotations, and “this term is no longer met as specialized researchers in the Islamic world. It was one of the decisions of the World Conferences Organization in its conference held in Paris in 1973, which dispensed with this term and called this organization (conferences). International)) ICHSANA The organization held two conferences under this title until it was changed again to (International Conferences for Asian and North African Studies) ICANAS (26): ((We will present them with scientific studies centered on the history of societies, the inhabitants of Eastern Europe are linked) (27). This Russian ArabistIgnatiKrachkovsky, who launched (Russian Orientalism) (B. Ostrog, Russian), says: The university decree was issued in 1804 because this decree He introduced the teaching of oriental languages in secondary schools and the establishment of program departments for these languages. As for the eastern languages of Western Europe at that time, the Hebrew language was the first among the Semitic languages. As for us in Russia, the eastern languages in the concept of Russians were the languages of the Islamic East, and occupied The Arabic language ranks first, and the Department of Arabic Language was established at Kharkov University immediately after the decree was issued in 1804(28) Hence the people who demand a change of term are their slanderers who insist on going back beyond it, but the negative images of Shrak need to be altered according to A and to change the term to be more precise and specialized in an exclusive study of the East. Muslim, as FH showed some Alpagesa n that e ((the

science that is exclusively concerned with the study of the Arab Mashreq. (29), so they are called Arab Mozarabs, or Islamic Islamists, or researchers in the humanities or social sciences for one of them. From the Arab countries d Abdul-Jabbar Naji defined the Arabists as those who are interested in studies related to the Middle East, including the study of languages, history and civilization related to it. (30) This Arab man is a researcher specializing in Islamism or a researcher in the humanities, and Al-Sharwani in HamadSmaillah Al-Asrab as follows: ((Science deals with the life of the Arabs and respects their civilization, literature, language, history and philosophies. Religions have their origins, branches, schools, characteristics, owners, followers, method, history, and goals)) (31) If we identify the beginnings of ambiguity and its manifestations, then we can say the beginnings in ((the era in which the Arabs And Islam cu sedition clearly appeared, but then it became an absolute Arabism in honor of schools and universities)) (32) Among these differences in the designation P en An important note is the motives and effects of these studies and research on the Islamic East.

B- Hidden causes

There are many hidden reasons that prompted some orientalists to call for changing the term Orientalism to other terms and summarize them as follows:

1. Economic reasons: Economic interests require the removal of obstacles and everything that is reflected in disturbing the economic and commercial process, neither Lord nor Western countries, since the only Arab and Islamic countries are the best market for markets. . After ditching the products, this prompted west to cement the relationship requesting E Lee's call for a term change.
2. The dialogue of civilizations led to the urgent need to change the term Orientalism due to the cultural cross-fertilization that the world may witness. Social networking sites had a clear impact, as they made the world from one village during which the West is slowly being introduced to peace despite the representation of some suspicious groups and the demand for peace only and that the whole onion is not from near or far.
3. Clarity of the political position and its acceptance of the influence of the West on the East, especially after the opening of political relations and the absence of a reason or justification for their orbits, even if some Arab parties are in solidarity with the political West. Spirit. Interests and coordination. I am about the government and the state, not about the influence of the major Western countries and our failure, in addition to the impact of settling the Israeli situation in Palestine, and the clarity of positions by some and the ruling Arab authorities because of the Palestinian issue, which has become ink on the Zad paper, including the issue of liberation, which expresses reconciliation and demands a change of term.
4. The religious reform led to the schism of the ecclesiastical church and the revolution of Martin Luther, which resonated with the separation of the broad religion from the pure state to win the church an example of indulgence and its example (33) and had a clear impact in reducing the dominance of religious fanatics haters and their relationship to the peace of peace.
5. Changing the strategy of control after the end of the colonial orientalist era and the transition from colonial influence, which is what was mentioned in the writings of many Orientalists Did the likes of Giladshahr and Dermanjim E. Lee criticize Orientalism, and the pain historically associated with PAL is different? May God's prayers and peace be upon him, the trial of the Prophet Muhammad in Sana'a for their words and efficiency in expanding the territories of their Islamic countries and transforming the bloody war into a cultural war, especially after the war, the commandment of the saint Louis XIX, who ((that there is no way to victory and overcoming Muslims from the power of soft war, because those condemned to peace lead them to resistance and jihad and make them restore God to the administration and preservation of peace. Dignity and dignity.. Muslims are always able to get out of their faith and Jihad to defeat the invaders. This must be another way, which is to change Islamic thought and tame Muslims through ideological conquest) (34)

And other reasons for calling contemporary orientalists to change the term.

The third requirement

The position of contemporary orientalist studies on the Holy Qur'an

Study of DmitriyFrolov as a model

We will present the demand with a statement of the position of contemporary Orientalist studies of the Holy Qur'an and then shed light on the study of the Russian Orientalist DmitriyFrolov as it is one of the studies presented at the conference and the demands to change the term.

First: The position of contemporary Orientalist studies of the Holy Qur'an

If we go back E.Lee works old Orientalists, we find: ((e n Orientalist work grew up in the shadow of the Crusades , and was subject to direct Christian clergy and their oversight appeared books bus accusations and claimed by a n There are three main lines of Ed T. E .Lee formation of the Koran , namely:

1. Information I got about Nestorian Christianity
2. Anti-Christian sentiments presented by a Jewish advisor to Muhammad
3. Deformations that occurred after the death of Muhammadr

The position of the Orientalists of Qara and Al-Tukub was reflected in their study of the various sciences and its history ((The early Orientalists used the entire planning process in their dealings with Islam with the aim of distorting its image and questioning it). And sometimes it is not acceptable (36), it is likely that the Orientalists put a certain idea in their minds and then search for evidence regardless of their origin and validity, and thus they fall into strange paradoxes.(37) Most of the contemporary Orientalist studies of the Holy Qur'an did not depart from the approach of the orientalist's predecessors. . ., and they were not able to abandon the assumptions and consequences that they put forward, so precedents state that contemporary Orientalism cannot be separated from ancient Orientalism, although there are serious attempts by some Orientalist contemporaries to improve the image of Orientalism in the world, Islam is the only one Which cannot be considered one of E Lee's peers, but their vision of Ro Ed in this field and he differed with them on some issues. Montgomery Watt mentions the position of contemporary Orientalists on the only peace where he says: (The ancestors of researchers since the twelfth century Yell the distorted picture generated in Alf and Lord of Eastern Peace, and despite the scholarly effort which is as such in E n it traces its weathered position to the fact that neo-medieval writings in Wallur still exist, and studies have not yet been able to avoid it) (39) Al-Madar Orientalist Studies of Jerusalem The Qur'an sees that the present cannot understand any ancient and different Orientalist approaches to thinking and some of the premises.

Second: The connotations of the stone in the Qur'an:the orientalist Dr .MimtriFrolovDimitry Frolov

In this request, we review the study of the Russian orientalist Dmitry Frolov as a model for the position of the Orientalists who demanded a change of term. This study is entitled "Signs of the Stone in the Noble Qur'an" and was submitted to the 35th Conference of Islamic Studies and North African Studies, which was held in 1997 AD. Before the writer touches on what the writer N. Six, showing the Qur'an's use of this word (Al-Hajj R.) and its meaning.

1- Quranic use of the word stone

Stone in the Holy Quran has multiple meanings. The word stone is mentioned in the Holy Qur'an in many places, and its connotations:

1- Good and soft

- He says: Moses' watering took me over his people. We said that he hit your stick with a stone (Al-Baqarah / 60).
- The Almi
- Ghty said: ((And we sent down on Moses, so he watered his people. They struck the stone with your stick) (Al-A'raf / 160).
- He says: ((There are stones from which rivers flow) (Al-Baqarah / 74).

2- Solutions to torment

- The Almighty's saying: ((So beware of the fire that people and stones eat) (Al-Baqarah / 24).
- The Almighty's saying: ((This is a right from you, so it rained stones from the sky)) (Al-Anfal: 34).
- The Almighty said: ((We made us inferior, so it rained on its stones from chains)) ((SuratHud / 82).
- The Almighty said: ((So let us drop stones at us)) (Al-Hijr: 74)
- He says: (You and your family differentiate between people and stoning) (Al-Tahrim 6).
- The saying of God Almighty: ((We send upon them stones of clay * marked, by your Lord, for extravagance (Al-Dhariyat / 33-34)
- The Almighty says: ((You throw stones at them from the trunk) (Surat Al-Fil / 4).

3- Barrier and barrier

- The Almighty said: (And they said: This is an ostrich that has plowed a stone that feeds only starch ((Al-An'am / 138)).
- The Almighty's saying: ((There is no human being on that day for criminals, and they say: The stone has been cut off) (Al-Furqan / 22).
- The Almighty's saying: ((And He placed between them an isthmus and a confined stone) ((Al-Furqan / 53)).
- The Almighty's saying: ((Verily, those who call upon you from behind the treasures, most of them do not understand) (Al-Hujurat / 4).

4- The mind

- The Almighty's saying: ((Verily, this is the rain)) (Al-Hijr / 5).

5- The name of the owners of Thamud

- He says: ((I love lying is the stone of the Messengers)) (Al-Hijr / 80).

2- The semantics of the stone in the Noble Qur'an in the study of Frolov

The study of the orientalist DimitryFrolov (The Stone in the Qur'an) was among the schemes I told them about in his study of the Stone in the Bible (When) and they went to it o It is an integrated series of the poetic image of the stone, which comes after the Holy Qur'an to complete the series, and places it in a step towards studying A comparison of different aspects of the depiction of a stone in the Bible for Christians, Jews and Muslims from

an exegetical perspective. Traditions. (40)MSI X Dmitry Stone is a multifaceted meaning in the New Testament, including:

- A symbol of choice associated with the upbringing of the Jewish people.
- The stone is also a symbol of holiness as a material for memorial, altar and temple
- The stone is the symbol of opposites "m out-hays ah". (41)

Dmitry Stone's study focused on several issues

- The connotations of the word stone in the Noble Qur'an and in books of interpretation such as al-Tabari, al-Zamakhshari, IbnKathir and al-Suyuti, and the goal is to prove the consistency between these interpretations and what. It was mentioned in the Old and New Testaments about the idea of stone. (42)This is the approach taken in the Old Testament with some connotations of the stone compared to what is found in Matthew and the Old Testament.

- History of some Qur'anic terms such as stone and stoning, attention to the issue of stoning, which occupies two-thirds of the meaning of the word stone in the Qur'an, and linking some Qur'anic issues to the Qur'an. a. The Old and New Testaments, which contain allusions that are not hidden from anyone (43).It should be noted in this study the link between the semantic stone, but Dmitri, in his study of the effects of the stone in the New Testament, denies the truth in the sense of stoning and God's punishment. Provided by law not obtained only once. (44)And from where is this convergence between what was mentioned in the Noble Qur'an and what is mentioned in the books of the Covenant, who is absent, as he put it, or simply referred to it? A: We have previously mentioned the meanings of the stone in the Noble Qur'an, and our luck in most cases is the punishment of God Almighty, not the strength of the deceived pervert.Dmitry Frolov took care of counting the number of times a word was mentioned and referred to the issue of the stone symbolic of life and death, referring to the spring of water from the stones and stoning that leads to death. (45)We note that the application of the orientalist Dimitri in his study tries to refer to the stone in the eras of books that follow the impact and fragility of the curriculum, and an attempt to exchange the application of the curricula used in their school books, the vows of the noble grave, and this approach is derived from the curriculum. Approaching the approach of his peers in analyzing the vocabulary of the Qur'an. The text, as it approaches the Russian Orientalist What is the Orientalist? Radwan's act (by analyzing the linguistic vocabulary and grammatical rules in the Qur'an, and claiming that the Qur'an is an unconscious compilation of Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be upon him and his family). The development of the meanings of some words with the emergence of new verses)) (46) the orientalist Dmitriy also raised the issue of painted stones, as he claimed that the Arabs took them from the Sumerians and Babylonians who were writing on clay. (47)What is noteworthy in this study is its attempt at semantics of stones due to the origins of Christianity, Judaism, and other ancient Babylonian civilizations. (48)

Findings and Recommendations

After the movements in the axes of the study and you came to save us through the results and recommendations of E. Lee, the tools are yes:

1. Many researchers and specialists in the words of studying the data of the orientalist in defining the term orientalism are a form of ambiguity and in order for the comprehensiveness of the East only to be the center in general and the Arab world in particular.
2. The pain was a limitation of the term if we know that the Middle East is linked to knowledge and science represented by the Arab Islamic Middle East is the request of the middle sciences represented in the Islamic Middle East.
3. The part of the Middle East is not geographically, and the East is linked to science and knowledge and exclusively reached areas with the wave of Islamic conquests after the Arab and Islamic conquests.
4. Changing the term orientalism and its continuation is not a matter to what extent it requires defining the stability and change of the foundations and principles of the Orientalists and Y for Orientalists they change Don's, whatever their positions are.
5. Intellectual premises for the spread of happiness, despite the calls for change, did not deny those that were dominated by developments only and the attempts of orientalist who demanded renewal associated with it. Way.
6. Most of the orientalist followed the approach of progress in the study of the Holy Qur'an, and the methods were not consistent with the objectives of their claims to change the term. This is evident in the study of the orientalist Dmitri Frolov, where he applies what he went through in his study for semantics. The stone in the two books of the Covenants MTB Amos: The approach of impact and weakness and the application of the critical approach used in studying the books of the Covenants and its application to the proper squash.
7. Invitations to change the pain for Z titles such as: A and researcher specialized in Shamash and other terms that Dr. Amos said to the international conference, we find most of them, and although I adopt this view and encourage them, but we find some researches that have been raised that contradict the principles of Changing the pain student as it kept it with its purpose and motivation - unintended in other Ohains - towards peace and the only Qur'an, did it change as AAS and c seekers of the apostolic path.

8. We invite researchers and specialists in the field of orientalist studies to follow up the contemporary studies of orientalists on Islam and the Noble Qur'an, study them in depth, and monitor the strengths and weaknesses of the curricula followed, which contributes to achieving this. Determining the general framework from which contemporary orientalists proceed.
9. The demanding contemporary orientalists change a term that is serious in applying their principles through their studies, and a high degree of objectivity in research does not achieve safety in the curricula and method on the one hand and proves to them. Intentions are disclosed to the other.

Margins

- IbnManzur, Lisan al-Arab: 10/173
- Same source, same page.
- Mazen Al-Mutabaqani, Orientalism: 3
- Rudi Barth, Arabic and Islamic Studies in German Universities: 11-12
- IbnManzur, Lisan Al Arab: 10/174
- Abdul-Jabbar Naji, The Development of Orientalism in the Study of the Arab Heritage: 23
- See: Abd al-Mutaal al-Jabri, Orientalism, the face of intellectual colonization: 7.
- Muhammad Baqir al-Hakim, Orientalists and their Suspicions of the Qur'an: 2/12.
- Arbery. British Orientalists: 8
- Rudi Barth, Arabic and Islamic Studies in German Universities: 11-12
- Muhammad Amin, Orientalists and the Holy Qur'an: 13
- Malik Bin Nabi, The Production of Orientalists and Its Impact on Modern Islamic Thought: 5-6
- Najeeb Al-Aqiqi, Orientalists: 3 / 216-349
- See: Saad Al-Hamid Objectives and Means of Orientalism: 2
- See: Farouk Omar Fawzi, Orientalism and Islamic History: 33-34
- Rudy Bart defined facilitation as: Convincing Muslims in their language of the invalidity of Islam and attracting them to the Christian religion. See: Muhammad Husayn al-Saghir, Orientalists and Quranic Studies: 15
- See: Saad Al-Hamid Objectives and Means of Orientalism: 4
- See: the same source: 6-7
- Quoted from: Abd al-Mu'attal al-Jabri, Orientalism, the face of intellectual colonization: 16-17.
- Among them: Muhammad Amin in the Orientalists and the Holy Qur'an: 39
- Mazen Al-Mutabaqani, Orientalism: 10
- Abd al-Mu'attal al-Jabri, Orientalism is an aspect of intellectual colonialism: 76-77
- Najeeb Al-Aqiqi Orientalists: 1149
- See: Saad Al-Hamid, The aims and means of Orientalism: 8
- See: Ali bin NayefUhud, Islamic Civilization between the Past and the Health of Future Hopes: 111-112.
- Mazen Al-Mutabaqani, Orientalism: 4-5
- SalihHashim, Orientalism between advocates and opponents: 113.
- KrachkovskyVralova, Studies in the History of the Arabization of Russia: 73
- Muhammad HamdiZaqzouq, Orientalism and the Intellectual Background of the Civilization Conflict: 18
- Abdul-Jabbar Naji, The Development of Orientalism in the Study of the Arab Heritage: 13
- Ahmed Smaifloush, The Philosophy of Orientalism: 34:
- Jalal Mazhar, Islamic Civilization: 150-151
- The issue of forgiveness is summed up in the fact that there are additional good works kept by the church, which is called the treasure of the church, and that some saints did good works sufficient only for their salvation, while others did many good works that exceeded their need, such as Christ, peace be upon him, and the Virgin Mary, peace be upon her, and the prophets and messengers. These works are kept in the church bank where they are considered. And she may dispose of these entrusted good deeds and distribute them to the souls who were unable to do the good deeds sufficient for their salvation in their lifetime. This theory was advocated by Alexander Hals in the thirteenth century and the Holy Thomas Aquinas. She had terms and conditions for getting it, but those terms changed and soon the subject was exploited and became a profitable business that the church turned to for money. See: Hanna Gergeres Al-Khudari, Reformer of Martin Luther's Life and Teachings: 60-61.
- Jariesheh Al-Zaibaq, Methods of Cultural Invasion: 19
- Mushtaq Bashir Al-Ghazali, The Holy Qur'an in Oriental Studies: 26
- Muhammad Muhammad Abu Laila, The Noble Qur'an from the point of view of the Orientalists: 401
- Mustafa al-Sibai, Orientalism and Orientalists: Their Money and Their Fate: 55
- See: Ali Ibrahim Al-Namlah, Orientalism and Islamic Studies: 132-133
- Quoted from: Riyad Al-Omari, The Methodology of Orientalists and Their Position on the Messenger, may God's prayers and peace be upon him: 62.
- АМЕНЬ В ЕВАНГЕЛИИ ОТ МАТФЕЯ Д. В. ФРОЛОВ, С. а. United States: 96

- Same source: 99
- See: MazinMutabaqani, Fifth International Conference on Asian and North African Studies, <http://www.saaaid.net/Doat/mazin/51.htm>
- See: same source
- Seen: КАМЕНЬ В ЕВАНГЕЛИИ ОТ МАТФЕЯ Д. В. ФРОЛОВ, С. а. United States: 99
- See: MazinMutabaqani, Fifth International Conference on Asian and North African Studies, <http://www.saaaid.net/Doat/mazin/51.htm>
- Quoted from: Elmir Raphael Koliev, The Book of the Qur'an and Its World by the Russian Orientalist YefimRadwan and his claims in the Book of God: 5
- Abd al-Rahman al-Ansari, quoted from: Mazen al-Mutabaqani, 35th International Conference on Asian and North African Studies, <http://www.saaaid.net/Doat/mazin/51.htm>
- See: What did the orientalist God Sheikh Noldeke go to refer to the vocabulary and teachings of the Noble Qur'an for what the Jewish writings carry, Theodore Noldeke: History of the Qur'an: 7

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